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Contributing partners: DTU, SSI, APHA, ANSES, ISS, PiWet, RIVM, VISAVET-UCM, WBVR

Other contributors: Clinical Microbiology Region Gävleborg, Halland and Uppsala, Sweden

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Author	Elina Lahti, Nadja Karamehmedovic, Hilde Riedel, Linnea Blom, Cecilia Jernberg		
Other contributors	Jeppe Boel, Yngve Dahlborg, Elisabetta Delibato, Martine Denis, Jenny Eriksson, María García, Aurora Garcia-Fernandez, Rene Hendriksen, Anna Heydecke, Renata Kwit, Claudia Lucarelli, Karl Lundin, Valeria Michelacci, Slawomir Owczarek, Isaac Ring, Ingegerd Sjögren, Mia Torpdahl, María Ugarte Ruiz, Kees Veldman, Eleonora Ventola, Lucas Wijnands, Magdalena Zajac		
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PILOT ISOLATION/DETECTION OF PATHOGENS

A CROSS-SECTORIAL PILOT PROFICIENCY TEST (PT)/EXTERNAL QUALITY ASSESSMENT (EQA) ON DETECTION AND CHARACTERISATION OF FOOD-BORNE PATHOGENS

1. Terms and definitions

BGA	Brilliant Green Agar
BHI	Brain Heart Infusion
BPW	Buffered Peptone Water
C1	CARE 1
C2	CARE 2
C3	CARE 3
C4	CARE 4
C5	CARE 5
CAT	Cephaloperazone Amphotericin B Teicoplanin agar
CIN	Cefsulodin Irgasan Novobiocin agar
EQA	External Quality Assurance
I ₂	Index of dispersion
ITC	Irgasan, Ticarcillin, Potassium Chlorate
Maldi-TOF	Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionisation - Time of Flight
mCCDA	Modified Charcoal Cephaloperazone Deoxycholate Agar
MkTTn	Muller-Kauffmann Tetrathionate Novobiocin
MSRV	Modified Semisolid Rappaport Vassiliadis
NMKL	Nordic Committee on Food Analysis
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PSB	Peptone Sorbitol Bile salts broth
PT	Proficiency test
RT	Room temperature
RV	Rappaport-Vassiliadis
SSDC	Salmonella Shigella Agar with Sodium Deoxycholate and Calcium Chloride
ST	Sequence type
T	Test of reproducibility
WGS	Whole-genome sequencing
XLD	Xylose Lysine Deoxycholate
XLT4	Xylose Lysine Tergitol 4
YeCM	Yersinia enterocolitica chromogenic media

2. Summary

Many different national and international sector specific Proficiency Test (PT)/External Quality Assessment (EQA) schemes exist designed to assessing the ability of the quality assured laboratories to detect and characterise food-borne enteropathogenic bacteria. However, cross sectorial joint panels for detection of food-borne zoonotic bacteria are lacking. The aim of this task within the OH EJP project CARE was to design, produce and launch a cross-sectorial PT/EQA pilot on detection and characterisation of the bacterial food-borne pathogens *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and/or *Yersinia* to assess the capacity of European laboratories to detect and characterise these bacteria. The objective of the PT was to prepare and use simulated samples to resemble those analysed at animal health, food, and public health laboratories. The test panel, consisting of five vials and a matrix, was set in an epidemiological context of a fictive outbreak scenario. In addition, the participants were asked to report if the findings of these pathogens were notifiable or not according to their national legislation or guidelines. All participants received the same matrix regardless of sector. The chosen matrix should ensure the same conditions regarding e. g. inhibitors, homogenisation issues or concentrations of the target pathogens that could influence the detection for the participants. All 12 EJP CARE participating institutes assigned to this work package and three other laboratories representing animal health, food and public health sectors from Denmark, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Sweden, and the United Kingdom participated and provided data.

All except one of the laboratories used accredited or quality assured methods for detection and characterisation. Almost all of the participants detected the target pathogens *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and *Yersinia enterocolitica* in samples of this PT/EQA. Regarding deviating results, the majority of false negatives, six out of seven, were reported for a sample spiked with *Salmonella* and *Yersinia enterocolitica* and the false negative results were reported by laboratories that did not use enrichment methods as part of routine methodology. The lack of enrichment, a lower concentration of the target organisms in the freeze-dried material and a smaller sample size, may explain the observed challenges in detection, especially in a complex background flora. Moreover, two false positive results were reported by different laboratories, one false positive for *Salmonella* and one false positive for *Campylobacter*. These results might have been a result of cross-contamination at the laboratory or a mistake in the reporting phase.

Especially on the public health side, more and more laboratories are moving from culture-based detection methods to molecular-based. In this PT/EQA, three public health laboratories reported having PCR as their primary detection method, followed by isolation via cultivation. Using PCR-based detection methods, test results can be available already after 2-3 hours whereas the culture-based methods can take from one up to several days. In general, rapid detection or exclusion of a bacterial gastrointestinal pathogen in a human, food and animal sample is highly requested for the patient, for the industry, for the authorities, and for the animal keeper. However, an isolate is still needed for species determination, subtyping and for susceptibility testing. The PCR results are often adequate for notification of a laboratory confirmed human case or for action by the food industry. Detection and characterisation of *Salmonella* from food and animal matrices, when using alternative methods such as PCR, is also allowed if the methods have been validated against the standard method. Information on which detection methods are allowed for notification is necessary when analysing cross-sectoral surveillance data. Some of the target organisms, depending on the sample matrix and national or EU legislation, could either be notifiable or not. As an example, six participants, reported that the notification of *Salmonella* was conditional, thus finding of a specific serovar or serovars would warrant notification in food or animals whereas other serovars would not. The notification practices for findings of *Yersinia* were the most limited on the food and veterinary side. In a food-borne outbreak investigation, findings of these pathogens would nevertheless be reported as part of the outbreak investigation.

A cross-sectoral PT/EQA set in an outbreak scenario could also be used as a trigger to increase awareness and understanding of the differences in detection methods and typing. For future cross-sectoral PTs/EQAs, the results from the panel could be discussed in a workshop format where the issues raised above could be lifted and described, in addition to a description of the results on detection of the target organisms per se.

In general, cross-sectoral panels within One Health can be a tool for increased awareness of differences in sector dependent surveillance data as well as be a tool for triggering discussions for improvement for harmonisation.

3. Background

This cross-sectoral Pilot Proficiency Test (PT)/External Quality Assessment (EQA) on detection and characterisation of bacterial food-borne pathogens was performed as a subtask (W1-T2-ST1 PT) within the One Health European Joint Programme (EJP) project CARE <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/jip-care/> and organised by the National Veterinary Institute (SVA) of Sweden, Public Health Agency of Sweden (FOHM) and Swedish Food Agency (SLV) during 2021. The aim of the PT/EQA was, together with the W1-T2-ST2 PT on typing and characterisation including whole genome sequencing (WGS) and W1-T2-ST3 PT on outbreak investigations based on WGS data, to provide recommendations for future cross-sectoral PTs/EQAs.

4. Introduction

National, regional, and local microbiological laboratories within food safety, animal health, and public health sectors may have different analytical approaches on when and how a sample would be analysed for enteropathogenic *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and/or *Yersinia*. The samples may, for instance, originate from official control programmes on food safety, or be part of an outbreak investigation, or from patients in hospitals or from outpatients for determination of an illness. In addition, after the laboratory analyses, the findings of the pathogens may have a different legal status regarding whether the finding is notifiable or not to a corresponding authority. All-in-all, these policy differences and differences in the collation of data can in a One Health perspective pose a challenge when cross-sectoral surveillance data is displayed between these sectors or between countries. Thereby, the context of the data needs to be explained to understand the results. Other tools to improve the possibility to compare data between the sectors and countries are, to a certain degree, to harmonize laboratory methods and/or testing the capacity for detection and identification of the relevant pathogens independently of the laboratory methods used. The pilot within this project is an attempt to test this capacity.

There are national and international sector specific PT/EQA schemes designed for assessing the ability to detect and characterise enteropathogenic bacteria, especially for *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* and to a certain extent for *Yersinia* in a quality assured manner. However, joint panels for detection of these food-borne zoonoses are lacking.

The aim of the pilot PT/EQA was to assess the cross-sectoral capacity of European laboratories to detect and characterise these three zoonotic foodborne bacteria. The objective was to prepare simulated samples to resemble matrices (samples) analysed at food, animal health and public health laboratories. Public health laboratories here refer to both the clinical microbiological laboratories (primary laboratories) and national public health laboratories. The laboratories were also asked to describe if findings of these pathogens were notifiable or not according to their national legislation or guidelines.

5. Outline of the proficiency test

The participants of the pilot PT/EQA were recruited among the partner institutions of the OH EJP CARE project (n=12). Additionally, three public health laboratories participated in the pilot from one of the partner countries. Of the 15 participating laboratories, five represented public health, five food safety, two animal health, two both food safety and animal health and one laboratory covered both public health and food safety. These categorisations are based on the information the participants reported.

The participants received a fictive scenario of a food-borne outbreak (Annex 1) and were assigned to analyse the samples for *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and *Yersinia* using the routine methods and practices applied at the laboratory. The participants were requested to detect the selected bacteria at a species level and include information of the serovar for *Salmonella* and bioserotype for *Yersinia* if the participants had methods available for these characterisations.

Each participant received five samples containing 35 mL of matrix (simulating a stool or a faecal or an environmental sample) and five vials containing freeze-dried bacteria (Table 2). Before analysing the samples, the vials with the freeze-dried bacteria were to be dissolved with 1 mL of sterile diluent and transferred to the matrix.

The participants were requested to report their results via a web-based questionnaire at the latest on the 31st of May 2021. In addition to questions on the results of the pilot PT/EQA, the web-based questionnaire included questions on the laboratory methods applied, on notification practices as well as the type of samples the laboratories usually receive (Annex 2).

5.1. Preparation and quality control of the matrix

The sample labelled “Matrix” represented an environmental sample from an abattoir or a stool sample or a composite environmental sample from wild boars, i.e. all laboratories received the same matrix composition. The matrix was prepared by dissolving 0.5 kg of autoclaved pig manure in 4 L sterilised buffered peptone water (BPW) (Oxoid LP0034) with NaCl (Merck 6404), mixed by swirling and then stored at +4 °C overnight. The following day, the solution was decanted and then autoclaved at +134 °C for 45 minutes. The matrix was stored at +4 °C until use.

Quality controls of the matrix were performed with cultivation methods and biochemical tests to analyse if *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Campylobacter coli*, *Salmonella* spp. or *Yersinia enterocolitica* were present above the detection limit that could influence the participants downstream results. In addition, the presence of *Salmonella* spp. was analysed using MicroSEQ™ *Salmonella* detection kit (Thermo Fisher, USA).

The cultivation methods and biochemical tests used to examine the matrix were performed according to the following methods from the Nordic Committee on Food Analysis (NMKL):

- Thermotolerant *Campylobacter*. Detection, semi-quantitative and quantitative determination in foods and drinking water. NMKL No. 119, 3. Ed., 2007
- *Salmonella*. Detection in foods. NMKL No 71, 5. Ed., 1999,
- *Yersinia enterocolitica*. Detection in foods. NMKL No. 117, 3. Ed., 1996

C. jejuni, *C. coli*, *Salmonella* spp. or *Y. enterocolitica* were not present above the detection limit in the matrix.

The matrix was tested on the BD MAX™ System (BD Diagnostics), a fully automated extraction and real-time PCR machine, using the BD MAX™ Enteric Bacterial Panel and BD MAX™ Extended

Enteric Bacterial Panel. The BD MAX™ System was not able to detect *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* or *Yersinia* in the matrix.

5.2. Production and quality control of the vials

Each participant received five vials with freeze-dried microorganisms, designated Care 1-5, hereinafter referred to as C1-5 (Table 1). *Yersinia enterocolitica* O:3/biotype 4 and biotype 1A are hereinafter abbreviated to O:3/BT4 and BT1A, respectively. Vials C1-4 were freeze-dried in portions of 0.5 mL, as described by Peterz and Steneryd (1993) using Epsilon 1-12 D (Christ, Osterode, Germany). C5 was freeze-dried using an ALPHA 1-4/LD PLUS (Christ, Osterode, Germany) in portions of 1 mL.

Quality control of the vials was performed on ten randomly selected vials in conjunction with manufacturing or on five vials if the sample mixture was already approved for homogeneity. Homogeneity of a sample mixture was approved if the values obtained for the test of reproducibility (T) and the test index of dispersion between vials (I_2) did not simultaneously exceed 2.6 and 2.0, respectively. (For definitions of T and I_2 , see references Mooijman et al. 2003 and Heisterkamp et al. 1993, respectively.) Approximate concentrations, as well as the I_2 and T values from the quality control of the sample mixtures, are listed below (Table 2).

Table 1. Microorganisms present in the vials. Bold font indicates target organisms.

Vial	Microorganisms
C1	<i>Campylobacter coli</i> , <i>Citrobacter freundii</i> , <i>Escherichia coli</i> O157 (stx neg) and <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>
C2	<i>Salmonella</i> Stockholm , <i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3/BT 4 , <i>Escherichia coli</i> and <i>Klebsiella rhizophila</i>
C3	<i>Salmonella</i> Enteritidis , <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> , <i>Escherichia coli</i> and <i>Staphylococcus saprophyticus</i>
C4	<i>Micrococcus</i> sp., <i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i> , <i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> , <i>Bacillus cereus</i> , <i>Candida</i> sp. And <i>Clostridium perfringens</i>
C5	<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> BT 1A

Table 2. Concentration mean (m), I_2 and T values from the quality control of the target organisms.

Vial ^a	Microorganism	Analysis ^b	m ^c	I_2	T
C1	<i>C. coli</i>	mCCDA, 37 °C, 48 h	3.7 10 ⁵	8.1	1.9
C2	<i>S. Stockholm</i>	BHI agar, 37 °C, 24 h	4.1 10 ^{4 d}	2.1	1.6
	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3/BT 4	BHI agar, 37 °C, 24 h	9.9 10 ^{4 d}	0.8	1.3
C3	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	BHI agar, 37 °C, 24 h	6.0 10 ^{4 d}	0.6	1.2
	<i>C. jejuni</i>	mCCDA, 37 °C, 48 h	5.6 10 ⁴	0.5	1.2
C5	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> BT 1A	BHI agar, 37 °C, 24 h	1.2 10 ⁵	-	-

^a Five vials for samples 1, 3 and 4 and ten vials for vial 2 and 5 were analysed in duplicate

^b mCCDA (Modified Charcoal Cephoperazone Deoxycholate Agar) and BHI (Brain Heart Infusion)

^c Concentration mean in cfu/mL

^d From analysis of a parallel sample mixture

5.3. Distribution of the PT/EQA

The participating laboratories were informed on January 5, 2021 via email about the anticipated number of samples and approximate time point (month) for the PT/EQA.

Samples were dispatched under refrigeration by courier in accordance with IATA packing instructions 650 for UN3373, on April 12, 2021. All 15 participants received five vials, five matrix samples, a temperature logging device, instructions, and a material safety data sheet (MSDS).

Instructions and a personal link for reporting were sent by email to the contact person(s) at each laboratory. The laboratories were instructed to initiate the analyses the same week the PT/EQA was received. The deadline for submitting the results was May 31, 2021.

Each laboratory was asked to analyse the samples according to the methods in use in their laboratory.

5.4. Methods for characterisation of the target organisms by the organisers

All target organisms were characterised with WGS (Table 3). Automated nucleic acid extraction and purification were performed with PSS MagLEAD 12gC (Precision System Science Co., Ltd, Chiba, Japan) and DNA concentration (ng/μL) was quantified with Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) prior to library preparation with the Ion Xpress Plus Fragment Library Kit for AB Library Builder System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA).

The libraries were quantified by an in-house real-time PCR assay (Beser et al., 2017) and later sequenced with an Ion GeneStudio S5 Prime system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The minimum average coverage depth was set to 20x and the expected mean read-length was 300 bp.

Quality trimming and assembly of the genome was performed with CLC assembly cell using the settings (clc_quality_trim --c -25 and clc_assembler -v -q -o) (CLC 2021). Species was identified by BLAST towards an in-house database with reference sequences (Camacho *et al.* 2009) and sequence type (ST) was determined using the seven-gene Multi Locus Sequence Typing (MLST) scheme from PubMLST for *Campylobacter* (Dingle et al., 2001), the Achtman 7 gene MLST scheme from Enterobase for *Salmonella* (Achtman *et al.* 2020, Alikhan et al., 2018, Zhou *et al.*, 2020) and the McNally 7 gene MLST scheme for *Yersinia* (Zhou et al. 2020).

A known sequence type was not obtained for *Yersinia enterocolitica* O:3/BT 4, CCUG45643, in vial C2, displaying the seven gene MLST allelic profile 6-2-3-3-2-3-?. Validation of automated MLST results was performed by mapping of the raw reads towards the first allelic sequence for each allele in the McNally 7 gene MLST scheme, followed by variant call using samtools/bcftools and consensus generation. The consensus sequences were then aligned with blastn towards a database of all current allelic sequences available under the scheme from Enterobase at 2021-11-29. The attained profile was 6-2-3-3-2-3-82, representing ST 276.

In silico serovar prediction for *Salmonella* was performed with an in-house database of STs and corresponding serovars in combination with SeqSero (Zhang et al., 2015).

Table 3. Characterisation of the target organisms with whole genome sequencing.

Vial	Microorganism	Reference ^a	Sequence type (ST)
C1	<i>C. coli</i>	CCUG 45147	ST860
C2	<i>S. Stockholm</i>	SLV-390	ST3214
	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3/BT 4	CCUG 45643	ST276
C3	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	SLV-436	ST11
	<i>C. jejuni</i>	SLV-540	ST21
C4	No target microorganisms		
C5	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> BT 1A	CCUG 46850	ST147

^a Culture collection (CCUG: Culture Collection University of Gothenburg, Sweden, SLV: Swedish Food Agency)

6. Results

6.1. Arrival of the PT/EQA and start of the analysis

The participants received the pilot PT/EQA on April 13, 2021 (13 participants) and April 14 (2 participants).

The analyses were initiated on April 13 (n=4), April 14 (n=3), April 14 and 15 (n=1), April 19 (n=4), May 13 (n=1), May 15 (n=1). One participant initiated the analysis of *Salmonella* on April 19, the analysis of *Campylobacter* and that of *Yersinia* on May 3, 2021. After arrival, the package was stored at refrigerator temperature (+ 3 - + 8°C) at 11 laboratories, in a freezer (-20°C) at two laboratories and at room temperature (+ 20 - + 22°C) at two laboratories. The laboratories that stored the package at room temperature initiated the analysis upon arrival.

6.2. Detection and characterisation

6.2.1. *Campylobacter* spp.

Of the 15 participating laboratories, 13 analysed the samples for *Campylobacter*. Eight participants performed enrichment prior to plating onto a selective medium. There were some differences between the laboratories whether one or two selective media were used for detection (Table 7), and whether one or several methods, MALDI-TOF, biochemical tests, microscopy, PCR and WGS were used for species identification (Table 8). In total, five laboratories used PCR for detection and characterisation of *Campylobacter* and one public health laboratory used the commercial real-time PCR system BD MAX™. The amount of the sample used for detection varied between 10 µL and 10 mL, the public health laboratories used smaller sample sizes (Table 7).

Campylobacter spp. were present in two vials, *C. coli* in C1 and *C. jejuni* in C3. Of the laboratories testing for *Campylobacter*, all 13 correctly detected the target in C1 (Table 4). Eleven laboratories reported the result at species level (*C. coli*), one at genus level and one as either *C. jejuni* or *C. coli*. Twelve of the laboratories testing for *Campylobacter* reported a correct detection result for C3. Ten laboratories reported the result at species level (*C. jejuni*), one at genus level and one as either *C. jejuni* or *C. coli*.

One false negative result was reported for sample C3 and one false positive result of *Campylobacter* spp. for sample C5. These results were reported by two different laboratories and the laboratory reporting the false negative result for sample C3 correctly detected *Campylobacter* in sample C1.

6.2.2. *Salmonella* spp.

All fifteen participating laboratories analysed the samples for *Salmonella*. Nine laboratories performed both pre-enrichment and enrichment prior to plating onto selective media (Table 9). Five

of the six laboratories that did not perform pre-enrichment belonged to the public health sector and two of them did not use any enrichment methods. The amount of the sample used for detection varied between 10 µL and 25 mL, the public health laboratories using smaller sample sizes (Table 9).

Species identification was performed using one or several of the methods: MALDI-TOF, biochemical tests, PCR and WGS (Table 10). Two public health laboratories used PCR for detection of *Salmonella*, one of them the commercial real-time PCR system BD MAX™.

Most laboratories performing serotyping of *Salmonella* used conventional slide agglutination according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor scheme (Table 10). Three laboratories used WGS for species identification and serotyping, either as a primary method or in addition to the other methods.

Salmonella spp. was present in two vials, *Salmonella* Stockholm in C2 and *Salmonella* Enteritidis in C3. Two laboratories from public health reported false negative results for *S. Stockholm* and were the only laboratories that did not use enrichment methods. The other laboratories detected *Salmonella* and nine of them reported serovar Stockholm. All laboratories detected *Salmonella* in sample C3 and nine laboratories reported serovar Enteritidis (Table 4).

One false positive result for *Salmonella* was reported for sample C4.

6.2.3. *Yersinia enterocolitica*

Of the 15 participating laboratories, eleven analysed the samples for *Yersinia* spp. Six laboratories used enrichment methods prior to plating onto a selective medium (Table 11). The laboratories not using any enrichment methods were from the public health sector. The amount of the sample used for detection varied between 10 µL and 25 mL, the public health laboratories using smaller sample sizes (Table 11).

Species and bioserotype identifications were performed by one or several of the methods: biochemical tests, MALDI-TOF, PCR and WGS (Table 12). Three public health laboratories used PCR for detection of *Yersinia enterocolitica*, one of them the real-time PCR for detection of *Y. enterocolitica* and one used the commercial real-time PCR system BD MAX™.

The target organism *Y. enterocolitica* was present in two vials: O:3/BT 4 in C2 and BT 1A in C5 (Table 3). The four laboratories not analysing *Y. enterocolitica* routinely belonged to the food or animal health sector.

Seven of the eleven participating laboratories correctly identified *Y. enterocolitica* in sample C2. Four of the laboratories reported the results at a bioserotype or serotype level, correctly assigning O:3/BT 4 or O:3 (Table 4). False negative results were reported by four public health laboratories not using enrichment methods in their routine methodology.

All eleven laboratories testing for *Yersinia* spp. identified *Y. enterocolitica* in sample C5, however, one of the laboratories obtained deviating results, reporting both *Y. enterocolitica* and *Campylobacter* spp. in the sample. Six of the eleven laboratories correctly reported biotype 1A.

Table 4. Results of the PT/EQA reported by the participants

Lab code	Vial							False negative results	False positive results
	C1	C2	C2	C3	C3	C4	C5		
L1	<i>C. coli</i>	S. Stockholm	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3/BT 4	S. Enteritidis	<i>C. jejuni</i>	No target microbes	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> BT 1A	0	0
L2	<i>C. coli</i>	S. Stockholm	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	S. Enteritidis	<i>C. jejuni</i>	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	0	0
L3	<i>C. coli</i>	S. Stockholm	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3/BT 4	S. Enteritidis	ND	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> BT 1A	1	0
L4	<i>C. coli</i>	S. Stockholm	ND	S. Enteritidis	<i>C. jejuni</i>	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> BT 1A	1	0
L5	<i>C. coli</i>	S. Stockholm	NA	S. Enteritidis	<i>C. jejuni</i>	ND	NA	0	0
L6	<i>C. coli</i>	S. Stockholm	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> O:3	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>C. jejuni</i>	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> non-pathogenic	0	0
L7	<i>C. coli</i>	ND	ND	S. Enteritidis	<i>C. jejuni</i>	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> BT 1A	2	0
L8	<i>C. coli/jejuni</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	ND	S. Enteritidis	<i>C. coli/jejuni</i>	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> non-pathogenic	1	0
L9	NA	S. Stockholm	NA	S. Enteritidis	NA	ND	NA	0	0
L10	<i>C. coli</i>	S. Stockholm	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> BT 4	S. Enteritidis	<i>C. jejuni</i>	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> BT 1A	0	0
L11	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>C. jejuni</i>	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	0	0
L12	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>C. jejuni</i>	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> non-pathogenic	0	0
L13	<i>Campylobacter</i> sp.	ND	ND	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>Campylobacter</i> sp.	ND	<i>Y. enterocolitica</i> <i>Campylobacter</i> sp.	2	1
L14	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	NA	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	NA	0	1
L15	NA	S. Stockholm	NA	S. Enteritidis	NA	ND	NA	0	0

NA= not analysed, ND = not detected

6.3. Additional information

Of the 15 participants, all, except one, were accredited or quality assured for detection of *Salmonella*, eleven for detection of *Campylobacter* and seven for *Yersinia*. Five of the six public health laboratories were accredited or quality assured for detection of all the three target pathogens. Of the 11 laboratories accredited or quality assured for detection of *Campylobacter*, five covered public health, three food safety, two animal health and one both animal health and food safety. Of the seven laboratories accredited or quality assured for detection of *Yersinia*, five covered public health and two food safety. No animal health laboratory was accredited or quality assured for detection of *Yersinia*.

Thirteen participants reported that detection of *Salmonella* was notifiable in their sector in their country (Table 5). However, six participants reported that the notification of *Salmonella* was conditional. For instance, detection of the serovars Enteritidis and Typhimurium were notifiable within food sector in one country and detection of Enteritidis, Typhimurium (and the monophasic variant), Hadar, Infantis, and Virchow in another country. Detection of *Campylobacter* was notifiable within the sector of eight of the participants though the notification could be dependent on the animal species and/or matrix. Detection of *Yersinia* was notifiable for six laboratories: five of these six laboratories covered public health. Two of the public health laboratories indicated that no pathogenic *Yersinia* was detected in sample C5, which was correct according to the notification criteria for these participants, since the target bacterium was *Y. enterocolitica* biotype 1A. These laboratories, indicated that they had detected the bioserotype in the sample.

Of the participants, all but two replied that they routinely received samples for detection of *Salmonella*, 11 for detection of *Campylobacter* and five for *Yersinia* (Table 6). Twelve of the participants received isolates of *Salmonella* for further characterisation, eight for *Campylobacter* and six for *Yersinia*.

Table 5. Notification of findings of *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and *Yersinia* within the public health, animal health and food safety sectors of the country according to the participants of the PT/EQA. Notifications may be dependent on the animal species, matrix, detection method, species and/or serovar.

Lab code	<i>Campylobacter</i>	<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>Yersinia</i>	Sector
L1	Yes	Yes	No	F + V
L2	Yes	Yes	No	F
L3	No	Yes	No	P + F
L4	No	Yes	Yes	P
L5	Yes	Yes	No	V
L6	Yes	Yes	Yes	F
L7	Yes	Yes	Yes	P
L8	Yes	Yes	Yes	P
L9	No	No	No	F + V
L10	No	Yes	No	F
L11	No	Yes	No	V
L12	Yes	Yes	Yes	P
L13	Yes	Yes	Yes	P
L14	No	No	No	F
L15	No	Yes	No	F

Table 6. Routinely performed detection and characterisation of *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and *Yersinia* within the public health, animal health and food safety sectors of the country according to the participants of the PT/EQA.

Lab code	<i>Campylobacter</i>		<i>Salmonella</i>		<i>Yersinia</i>		Sector
	Detection	Characterisation	Detection	Characterisation	Detection	Characterisation	
L1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	F + V
L2	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	F
L3	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	P + F
L4	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	P
L5	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	V
L6	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	F
L7	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	P
L8	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	P
L9	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	F + V
L10	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	F
L11	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	V
L12	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	P
L13	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	P
L14	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	F
L15	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	F

7. Discussion

This pilot PT/EQA is, to the authors' knowledge, the first cross-sectoral PT/EQA organised on detection and characterisation of bacterial food-borne pathogens in matrices simulating samples analysed within public health, animal health and food safety.

All but one of the participating laboratories used accredited or quality assured methods for detection and characterisation. Most participants detected the target pathogens *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and *Yersinia enterocolitica* in the samples C1, C2, C3 and C5 of this PT/EQA. Regarding deviating results, the majority of reported false negatives, six out of seven, were reported for sample C2 including the target bacteria *Salmonella* Stockholm and *Yersinia enterocolitica* O:3/BT 4 and concentrated to public health laboratories not using enrichment methods as part of routine methodology in addition to using smaller sample sizes. The absence of enrichment, a smaller sample size and a lower concentration of target organisms in this sample, may explain the observed challenges in detection, especially in a complex background flora as faeces.

The number of bacteria in the vials used in the PT/EQA varied between 4.1×10^4 and 3.7×10^5 cfu/mL. When analysing food samples or animal samples for asymptomatic carriers for *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* or enteropathogenic *Yersinia* the aim is to detect low levels of these bacteria. On the contrary, when clinical samples are analysed, the detection limit does not need to be as low. Thus, for detection in animal and food matrices by using enrichment methods, the pilot PT/EQA was probably not challenging whereas for public health laboratories not applying an enrichment step, the levels of 10^4 cfu/mL could be close to the detection limit. However, detection of *Campylobacter* at the same levels was not problematic.

Moreover, a total of two false positive results were reported by different laboratories, one false positive for *Salmonella* and one false positive for *Campylobacter*. These results might have been a result of cross-contamination at the laboratory or a mistake in the reporting phase.

On the public health side, more and more laboratories are moving from culture-based detection methods to PCR-based. Using PCR or other molecular-based methods test results can be available already after 2-3 hours if an enrichment is not applied whereas the culture-based methods can take from one up to several days. Many laboratories do not necessarily proceed further after the PCR step and isolation attempts may be only performed when antibiotic resistance needs to be assessed or when treatment is needed, typing for outbreak investigations, or for targeted surveillance. The PCR results are often enough for notification as a criteria for a laboratory confirmed case, as the ECDC case definitions show (ECDC 2018). For detection and characterisation of these pathogens from food and animal matrices, according to the EU Control Regulation 2017/625, the use of standard methods is preferable and alternative methods, such as PCR, are allowed if the methods are validated against the standard method according to ISO 16140-6:2019.

Three of the public health laboratories used multiplex PCR as the primary detection method, either a commercial system or an in-house method. The BD MAX™ system for enteric pathogens was used by one laboratory. This was done without performing any enrichment of the samples. Andersson et al. (2014) showed that the BD MAX™ system demonstrated 100% sensitivity for *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Salmonella* spp. tested at the following concentrations of bacteria in a sample (artificially produced by mixing stool samples with bacteria): 10^7 cfu/mL, 10^6 cfu/mL and 10^5 cfu/mL. At 10^4 cfu/mL the sensitivity of BD MAX™ was 100% for *Campylobacter jejuni* but only 69% for *Salmonella* spp. and 44% at 10^3 cfu/mL, which might explain the difficulties with detecting *Salmonella* sp, but not *Campylobacter* spp. (*Campylobacter jejuni* or *Campylobacter coli* in the pilot PT/EQA).

Berenger BM et al. 2021, demonstrated poor performance of *Yersinia enterocolitica* detection and lack of *Yersinia non-enterocolitica* detection assessing four commercially available real-time PCR system, including the BD MAX™ system. The poor agreement observed in the study of the four systems for detection of *Yersinia enterocolitica* might be explained by known heterogeneity between strains and different choices of chromosomal target genes such as *ail* and *ystB* (Thoerner P et al. 2003). The target gene for *Yersinia* in the BD MAX™ system is *invA* which is also present in non-pathogenic *Yersinia* (*Y. enterocolitica* BT1A). There are other commercial PCR systems where the target gene is *ail*, which will, with few exceptions, exclude *Y. enterocolitica* BT1A. There is an international standard ISO/TS 18867 for the detection of pathogenic *Y. enterocolitica* in the food chain where the target gene is *ail*.

In general, rapid detection or exclusion of a bacterial gastrointestinal pathogen in a human, food and animal sample is highly requested for the patient, for the industry and the animal keeper. However, an isolate is still needed for species determination, subtyping and for susceptibility testing. In future, there will be further developments of metagenomics methods which currently are used more for research purposes and/or for sample materials that under normal circumstances are sterile. With this method, all genetic material is amplified which makes the possibility to detect a specific organism within the normal flora of a faecal sample still too complex for the present bioinformatics tools. Metagenomics will, however, in the future probably minimize the need for cultivation of microorganisms for typing purposes, also for faecal samples.

According to the responses from the PT/EQA participants, the notification practices varied between pathogens, sectors and countries. Notification of all these three pathogens was most common within public health. Findings of *Salmonella* were notifiable within the sector in the country of 13 participants although the notification could be conditional. Finding of *Campylobacter* was notifiable within the sector of eight participants but findings of *Yersinia* in animal samples were not notifiable in any of the countries. However, in a food-borne outbreak investigation, the findings of these pathogens would nevertheless be reported as part of the outbreak investigation.

The matrix in the present panel was the same independent of the sector recipient. This matrix was chosen to enable the same conditions regarding inhibitors, homogenisation issues, concentrations of the target pathogens that could influence the detection for the participants. One could also consider having different matrices, consisting the same target pathogens if the sensitivity within the specific matrix would be an important aspect to cover.

The panel was set in an epidemiological context of an outbreak scenario. Having a cross-sectoral panel put in an outbreak scenario could be used as a trigger for further discussions between the participants which could give an increased awareness of the different sectors methods for detection, further typing, in addition to differences in notification. For future cross-sectoral panels, the results from the panel could be discussed in a workshop format where the issues raised above could be lifted and described, in addition to a description of the results on detection of the target organisms per se.

The target food-borne zoonotic organisms for future panels could also have specific resistance profiles, that could be part of the testing capacity. There can be different approaches for phenotypic testing of antibiotic resistance between different sectors. In addition, using WGS for predicted antibiotic resistance has increased during the last years for e. g. *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*. WGS for determination of antibiotic resistance would primarily be used for surveillance purposes (EFSA 2019) and not for assessing treatment regimens as the correlation between phenotypic and genotypic methods do not fully correlate.

In conclusion, this pilot PT/EQA showed that a cross-sectoral approach can be used for assessment of the One Health capacity to detect and characterise food-borne pathogens.

8. List of Appendices

Appendix 1: Pilot Proficiency Test (PT)/External Quality Assessment (EQA) on detection and characterisation of food-borne pathogens – Instructions

Appendix 2: Results reporting form

Appendix 3: Tables

9. References

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Appendix 1

Pilot Proficiency Test (PT)/External Quality Assessment (EQA) on detection and characterisation of food-borne pathogens - Instructions

One Health European Joint Programme (EJP) CARE IA 2.1-WP1-T2

Pilot Proficiency Test (PT)/External Quality Assessment (EQA) on detection and characterisation of food-borne pathogens

Starting the week no. 15, 12-16 April 2021

Data entry is open until 31 May 2021

General information

The objective of this cross-sectorial pilot proficiency test (PT)/ external quality assessment (EQA) is to assess the ability to detect and characterise enteropathogenic *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and *Yersinia* in samples simulated to resemble matrices analysed at food, veterinary and public health laboratories. The aim of this PT/EQA is, together with the W1-T2-ST2 PT on typing and characterisation including whole genome sequencing (WGS) and W1-T2-ST3 PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data, to provide recommendations for future cross-sectorial PTs/EQAs. These three pilot PTs/EQAs are organised within the One Health European Joint Programme project CARE <https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-care/>.

This PT/EQA is voluntary and free of charge. The participants may decide to perform the PT/EQA for one or all of these three pathogens.

The PT/EQA will be dispatched on Monday, April 12, 2021. The PT/EQA should be started the same week as the test is dispatched from the Swedish Food Agency in Uppsala, Sweden. All results shall be reported in a web-based questionnaire at the latest on **May 31, 2021**.

Information on the fictive epidemiological setting

Five persons visited their local general practitioner (GP) with symptoms ranging from severe stomach aches to diarrhoea lasting for more than four days. Four of the cases had participated in a weekend event involving hunting of wild boar. Besides hunting, the event included a tour to the neighbouring small abattoir and an all-inclusive castle hotel visit. The fifth case had delivered chicken and vegetables from a nearby farm to the event and had had a quick lunch at the castle. The weekend event hosted 15 guests, where three additional guests had reported mild gastrointestinal symptoms, which did not involve a visit to the GP.

Samples were sent for analysis targeting any of the gastrointestinal bacterial pathogens *Salmonella*, *Yersinia*, and *Campylobacter*.

- **Five stool samples** were sent to a clinical microbiological laboratory, four from the guests and a fifth from the neighbouring chicken farmer.
- **Five environmental samples** were sent to a food safety laboratory were obtained from the castle and abattoir: from floor drains and surfaces.
- **Five composite environmental samples** were sent to a veterinary laboratory from the wild boar baiting area, manure from the abattoir floor and from the neighbouring chicken farm.

Outline

Each participant will receive a package containing:

Five samples: each containing a sample labelled Matrix mimicking an environmental sample from an abattoir, or a stool sample or a composite environmental sample from wild boars. Each sample contains 35 ml of matrix. Thus, it is possible to use a test portion of 10 g for the analysis of each of the target organisms.

Five vials coded CARE 1-5 containing freeze-dried bacteria. The vials may contain one to three of the target organisms *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and/or *Yersinia* and background flora.

Enclosed with the PT/EQA is a temperature logging device, T-log, which is a small chip in a plastic bag. It is marked with a number which you do *not* need to record.

Please do not open the plastic bag, send it as soon as possible to

National Veterinary Institute (SVA)

Linda Svensson

ESS

751 89 Uppsala

Sweden

You can send it by regular mail in a regular envelope to this address.

On arrival, examine the package to ensure that it has not been damaged during the transport. Record the condition for later report in a web-based questionnaire.

We recommend you analyse the samples according to the methods (cultural or molecular methods) in use at your laboratory. You may also analyse the samples according to another method than your standard method. For *Campylobacter*, please perform a species identification, for *Salmonella* a result of the serovar and for *Yersinia* a biotype, if you have methods available for these characterisations. If you normally do not perform serotyping, species identification or biotyping, please report your results and procedures in the reporting form. Please describe the method(s) in the reporting form.

Please report the results as well as respond to the questions in the report form in the web-based questionnaire at the latest on the **31st of May 2021**. A personal link to the questionnaire will be sent by email in connection with the distribution of the PT/EQA to the contact person.

Preparation of the vials and the sample

Prepare the samples from the vials and the samples according to the instructions below.

1. To dissolve the vial with freeze-dried bacteria, remove the cap of the vial: with the arrow on the cap pointing away from you, carefully pull the flip top up and away from you. When the flip top is vertical pull downwards and either to the left or right until the seal separates. Gently remove the cap from the vial and dispose it in a container for sharp/cutting items. Please note this action may cause a distortion of the rubber stopper initiating a release of vacuum.
2. Reconstitute each vial in turn by aseptically adding 1 ml of Buffered Peptone Water or Phosphate Buffered Saline Buffer (or 0.9% of physiological saline).
3. Mix the suspension gently but thoroughly, and then transfer the suspension to the tube containing the mimicked sample.
4. Mix the sample and the suspension thoroughly and then continue the analyses of the sample according to the protocols routinely used in your laboratory for detection of *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and *Yersinia*.

We wish you good luck with the pilot PT/EQA!

Appendix 2

Results reporting form

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EJP CARE IA 2.1-WP1-T2

1) Contact Information

* Name of the institute/organisation

* Name of the contact person(s)

* E-mail(s)

2) Sector

- Clinical (public health) microbiology
- Food safety
- Veterinary medicine

3) * Date of arrival, time of arrival

Arrival |

4) * The condition of the samples and packaging on arrival

- OK
- Damaged

This box is shown in preview only.

The following conditions must be fulfilled for this question to be shown:

If the question "The condition of the samples and packaging on arrival" contains any of these alternatives

- "Damaged"

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5) * If damaged, please specify

6) * Storage temperature at the laboratory after arrival (°C)

7) * Starting date(s) of the analyses (dd/mm/yyyy)

8) * Accreditation of the laboratory

- Yes
- No

This box is shown in preview only.

The following conditions must be fulfilled for this question to be shown:

- If the question "Accreditation of the laboratory" contains any of these alternatives
 - "Yes"

9) * Are the methods for detection ACCREDITED for..?

	Yes	No
Campylobacter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salmonella	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Yersinia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

This box is shown in preview only.

The following conditions must be fulfilled for this question to be shown:

- If the question "Campylobacter" contains any of these alternatives
 - "No"

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or

If the question "Salmonella" contains any of these alternatives

- "No"

or

If the question "Yersinia" contains any of these alternatives

- "No"

10) * Are the methods for detection **QUALITY ASSURED** for..?

	Yes	No
Campylobacter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salmonella	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Yersinia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

11) * Do you receive samples from external clients for **DETECTION** of...

	Yes	No
Campylobacter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salmonella	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Yersinia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

12) * Do you receive samples from external clients for **CHARACTERISATION** of...

	Yes	No
Campylobacter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salmonella	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Yersinia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

This box is shown in preview only.

The following conditions must be fulfilled for this question to be shown:

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If the question "Campylobacter" contains any of these alternatives

- "Yes"

or

If the question "Salmonella" contains any of these alternatives

- "Yes"

or

If the question "Yersinia" contains any of these alternatives

- "Yes"

or

If the question "Campylobacter" contains any of these alternatives

- "Yes"

or

If the question "Salmonella" contains any of these alternatives

- "Yes"

or

If the question "Yersinia" contains any of these alternatives

- "Yes"

13) * If you receive samples or isolates for detection of characterisation, for which reasons do you receive them?

- As routine samples
- As part of an outbreak investigation
- Other

This box is shown in preview only.

The following conditions must be fulfilled for this question to be shown:

- If the question "If you receive samples or isolates for detection of characterisation, for which reasons do you receive them?" contains any of these alternatives
- "Other"

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14) * If other, please specify

This box is shown in preview only.

The following conditions must be fulfilled for this question to be shown:

If the question "Campylobacter" contains any of these alternatives

- "Yes"

15) * If you receive samples for detection for CAMPYLOBACTER what kind of matrices to you receive?

This box is shown in preview only.

The following conditions must be fulfilled for this question to be shown:

If the question "Salmonella" contains any of these alternatives

- "Yes"

16) * If you receive samples for detection for SALMONELLA what kind of matrices to you receive?

This box is shown in preview only.

The following conditions must be fulfilled for this question to be shown:

If the question "Yersinia" contains any of these alternatives

- "Yes"

17) * If you receive samples for detection for YERSINIA what kind of matrices to you receive?

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18) * Do you send suspected Isolates of Campylobacter, Salmonella or Yersinia to another laboratory for confirmation or subtyping?

	Yes	No
Campylobacter	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salmonella	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Yersinia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

19) * Is the detection of CAMPYLOBACTER notifiable in your sector in your country?

Yes No

20) Please specify if the notification depends on the sampler, species, matrix, detection method (culture, pcr, serology) or other reasons

21) * Is the detection of SALMONELLA notifiable in your sector in your country?

Yes No

22) Please specify if the notification depends on the sampler, species, matrix, detection method (culture, pcr, serology) or other reasons

23) * Is the detection of YERSINIA notifiable in your sector in your country?

Yes No

24) Please specify if the notification depends on the sampler, species, matrix, detection method (culture, pcr, serology) or other reasons

INFORMATION ON THE ANALYTICAL METHODS USED IN THE PT/EQA

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-
Campylobacter

25) * Sample size for analysis: a loopful (10 µl), 1 g, 5 g, 10 g or other

METHOD(S) FOR DETECTION

26) If cultivation, please describe

27) If PCR, please describe

28) If other, please specify in comments

ENRICHMENT

29) * Pre-enrichment before primary analysis?

Yes No

30) * Enrichment?

No Yes

CONFIRMATION AND SPECIES IDENTIFICATION

31) Method(s) for confirmation and species identification

INFORMATION ON THE ANALYTICAL METHODS

-
Salmonella

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32) * Sample size for analysis: a loopful (10 µl), 1 g, 5 g, 10 g or other

METHOD(S) FOR DETECTION

33) If cultivation, please describe

34) If PCR, please describe

35) If other, please specify in comments

ENRICHMENT

36) * Pre-enrichment before primary analysis?

Yes No

37) * Enrichment?

Yes No

CONFIRMATION, SPECIES IDENTIFICATION AND SEROTYPING

38) Method(s) for confirmation and species identification

39) Method for serotyping?

INFORMATION ON THE ANALYTICAL METHODS

Yersinia

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40) * Sample size for analysis: a loopful (10 µl), 1 g, 5 g, 10 g or other

METHOD(S) FOR DETECTION

41) If cultivation, please describe

42) If PCR, please describe

43) If other, please specify in comments

ENRICHMENT

44) * Pre-enrichment before primary analysis?

Yes No

45) * Enrichment?

Yes No

SPECIES IDENTIFICATION AND BIOTYPING

46) Method for species identification

47) Method for biotyping?

Results of the pilot PT/EQA

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48) Sample ID 001

Detected target bacteria (genus)	<input type="text"/>
Species identification	<input type="text"/>
Serotype/biotype	<input type="text"/>
Comments	<input type="text"/>

49) Sample ID 002

Detected target bacteria (genus)	<input type="text"/>
Species identification	<input type="text"/>
Serotype/biotype	<input type="text"/>
Comments	<input type="text"/>

50) Sample ID 003

Detected target bacteria (genus)	<input type="text"/>
Species identification	<input type="text"/>
Serotype/biotype	<input type="text"/>
Comments	<input type="text"/>

51) Sample ID 004

Detected target bacteria (genus)	<input type="text"/>
Species identification	<input type="text"/>
Serotype/biotype	<input type="text"/>
Comments	<input type="text"/>

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52) Sample ID 005

Detected target bacteria
(genus)

Species identification

Serotype/biotype

Comments

53) General comments on the PT

0/4000

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Appendix 3

Tables

Table 7. Sample size, enrichment and selective medium used for detection of *Campylobacter* spp.

Lab code	Sector	Sample size	Yes/No	Enrichment			Selective medium				
				Medium	Temperature	Period	Medium1	Medium2	Temperature	Period	Atmosphere
L2	F	10 mL	Yes	Bolton	41.5°C	48 h	mCCDA	Karmali	41.5°C		Microaerophilic
L6	F	10 mL	Yes	Bolton	41.5°C	48 h	mCCDA			48 h	
L10	F	10 mL	Yes	Preston	41.5°C	24 h	mCCDA	Butzler	41.5°C	48 h	Microaerophilic
L14	F	10 µL	Yes	Preston	41°C	24 h	mCCDA		41°C	48 h	Microaerophilic
L15	F	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*
L1	F + V	10 mL**	No				mCCDA		41.5°C	48 h	Microaerophilic
L9	F + V	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*
L5	V	10 µL	Yes	Preston	41.5°C	48 h	mCCDA	CAT	41.5°C	48 h	Microaerophilic
L11	V	10 mL	Yes	Preston	41.5°C	24 h	mCCDA	Butzler	41.5°C	48 h	Microaerophilic
L3	P + F	10 mL	Yes	Bolton			mCCDA	Non-selective blood free medium	42°C, 37°C	48 h	
L4	P	20 µL	No				mCCDA		37°C	48 h	Microaerophilic
L7	P	100 µL	No				CUP		37°C	72 h	Microaerophilic
L8	P	10 µL	No				mCCDA		42°C	48 h	Microaerophilic
L12	P	10 µL	Yes				Nonselective plate with cefuroxime		42°C		
L13	P	10 µL	No								

*Analysis not performed, **A wet swab from the samples was streaked onto selective media

D.1.2.1_Pilot isolation/detection of pathogens

Table 8. Species identification of *Campylobacter* spp.

Lab code	Sector	Species identification	If PCR, reference	Comments
L2	F	MALDI-TOF		
L6	F	Biochemical tests		From mCCDA to Blood Agar for confirmation.
L10	F	Biochemical tests, PCR	Wang et al. 2004	ISO 10272-1:2017
L14	F	WGS		
L15	F	NA*	NA*	
L1	F + V	Multiple PCR	Ugarte-Ruiz et al., 2012	If suspected colonies were found, streaked them onto blood agar 37°C for 48 h following microaerobic conditions
L9	F + V	NA*	NA*	
L5	V	MALDI-TOF		
L11	V	MALDI-TOF	ISO 10272-1	
L3	P + F	Multiplex PCR	DNA extraction by chelex and multiplex PCR (Denis M. et al. Letters in Applied Microbiology 1999, 29, 406-410)	100 ul of the pre-enrichment culture pipetted to the centre of a 0.65 µm membrane filter placed on the surface of an mCCDA plate and on a non-selective blood agar. Incubation in a microaerophilic atmosphere for 48 h, at 42 °C and 37°C , in parallel.
L4	P	MALDI-TOF		
L7	P	MALDI-TOF, WGS		
L8	P	Biochemical tests, MALDI-TOF, Microscopy		
L12	P	MALDI-TOF, PCR	In-house PCR, target genes <i>ceuE</i> (<i>C. coli</i>) and <i>mapA</i> (<i>C. jejuni</i>)	Culture of positive PCR samples only, on a rich non-selective plate, with cefuroxim disc, in 42°C.
L13	P	MALDI-TOF, PCR	BD MAX system (extraction and PCR) using enteric bacterial kit and extended enteric bacterial kit.	

*Analysis not performed

Table 9. Sample size, enrichment and selective medium used for detection of *Salmonella* spp.

Lab code	Sector	Sample size	Pre-enrichment				Enrichment				Selective medium			
			Yes/No	Medium	Temperature	Period	Yes/No	Medium	Temperature	Period	Medium1	Medium2	Temperature	Period
L2	F	10 mL	Yes	BPW	37°C	24 h	Yes	MSRV	41.5°C	24 h	XLD		37°C	24 h
L6	F	10 mL	Yes	BPW	37°C	24 h	Yes	RV	42°C	24 h	XLD	BGA		
L10	F	25 mL	Yes	BPW	37°C	24 h	Yes	MSRV, MktTn	41.5°C	24 h	XLD	XLT4	37°C	24 h
L14	F	10 µL	No				Yes	MSRV	41°C	24 h	XLD	BGA	37°C	24 h
L15	F	10 mL	Yes	BPW	37°C	24 h	Yes	MSRV, MktTn	41.5°C	24 h	XLD	BGA	37°C	24 h
L1	F + V	10 mL	Yes	BPW	37°C	18-24 h	Yes	MSRV	41.5°C	24 h±3 up to 48h±3	XLD	SMID2	37°C	24 h±3
L9	F + V	10 µL	Yes	BPW	37°C	16-20 h	Yes	MSRV	41.5°C	24 h±3	XLD,BGA, novo	Rambach	37°C	24 h±3
L5	V	25 mL	Yes	BPW	37°C	24 h	Yes	MSRV	41.5°C	24 h	XLD	BGA	37°C	24 h
L11	V	10 mL	Yes	BPW	37°C	24 h	Yes	MSRV	41.5°C	24 h	XLD	BGA	37°C	24h
L3	P + F	25 mL	Yes	BPW			Yes	RV, MktTn	42°C (RV)/ 37°C (MktTn)	24 h	XLD	Chrom-agar	37°C	
L4	P	20 µL	No				Yes	Selenite	37°C	24 h	Red agar		37°C	24 h
L7	P	100 µL	No				No				Basic agar	DC agar	37°C	24 h
L8	P	10 µL	No				Yes	RV	42°C	24 h	XLD		35°C	24 h
L12	P	10 µL	No				Yes	RV	40°C		XLD			
L13	P	10 µL	No				No							

*Analysis not performed

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Table 10. Species identification and determination of serovar of *Salmonella* spp.

Lab code	Sector	Species identification	Serotyping	Comments
L2	F	ISO 6579-1:2017-04	ISO 6579-1:2017-04	EN ISO 6579-1:2017-04
L6	F	Biochemical tests	Classical slide agglutination	Pre-enrichment with BPW for 18-20 h in 37°C. 100 ul transfer to RVS-broth and Incubation for 24 h in a in 42°C water bath. From RVS a loopful is streaked on agar BriS and XLD.
L10	F	Biochemical tests	Classical slide agglutination	NF U 47-100
L14	F	WGS		
L15	F	Biochemical tests, WGS	WGS, classical slide agglutination	EN-ISO 6579-1:2017
L1	F + V	Biochemical tests	Classical slide agglutination	ISO 6579 (primary production protocol). Confirmation according to ISO 6579-1:2017
L9	F + V		Classical slide agglutination	EN-ISO 6579-1:2017
L5	V	Biochemical tests, MALDI-TOF	Classical slide agglutination	
L11	V	MALDI-TOF		
L3	P + F		Classical slide agglutination	0,1 ml of pre-enrichment + 10 ml of RVS and 1 ml of pre-enrichment + 10 ml of MKTTn (selective enrichment)
L4	P	Biochemical tests, MALDI-TOF	WGS, classical slide agglutination	
L7	P	MALDI-TOF, WGS	WGS, classical slide agglutination	
L8	P	MALDI-TOF	Classical slide agglutination	Day one: XLD agar (24 h in 35°C) and Rappaport enrichment broth (24 h in 42°C). Day two: cultivation to XLD from Rappaport broth (24 h in 35°C)
L12	P	MALDI-TOF, PCR		In-house PCR
L13	P	PCR		BD MAX system (extraction and PCR) using enteric bacterial kit and extended bacterial kit

*Analysis not performed

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Table 11. Sample size, enrichment and selective medium used for detection of *Yersinia enterocolitica*.

Lab code	Sector	Sample size	Pre-enrichment				Enrichment				Selective medium							
			Yes/No	Medium	Temperature	Period	Yes/No	Medium	Temperature	Period	Medium1	Temperature	Period	Medium2	Temperature	Period		
L2	F	1 mL	Yes	PSB	5°C	14 d	Yes					CIN	29°C	24 h				
L6	F	10 mL	Yes				Yes	PSB	25°C	3 h		CIN	30°C	24 h				
L10	F	25 mL	No				Yes	PSB/ITC	25°C	48 h		CIN	30°C	24 h				
L14	F	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*
L15	F	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*
L1	F + V	10 mL	Yes	PSB	25°C	5 d	Yes	ITC	25°C	48 h		YER	30°C	48 h	SSDC	30°C	48 h	
L9	F + V	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*
L5	V	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*	NA*
L11	V	10 mL	No				Yes	ITC	22°C	2 d		CIN	30°C	2 d				
L3	P + F	25 mL	No				Yes	PSB	25°C	48 h		CIN	30°C	48h	Chromogenic Yersinia agar	30°C	48 h	
L4	P	20 µL	No				No					SSI Diagnostica Red agar plate	37°C	24 h				
L7	P	100 µL	No				No					Basic agar	37°C	24 h	DC agar	37°C	24 h	
L8	P	10 µL	No				No					CIN	30°C (day1) RT (day2)	24 h + 24 h				
L12	P	10 µL	No				No					CIN	30°C	1-2 d				
L13	P	10 µL	No				No											

*Analysis not performed

Table 12. Species identification and determination of biotype of *Yersinia enterocolitica*.

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research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Lab code	Sector	Species identification	Comments
L2	F	MALDI-TOF	Pre-enrichment: 10 ml of sample added into 90ml PSB broth, incubated at 5°C (14 days), 10 µl subculture suspended in solution 0.25% KOH in 0.5% NaCl, mixed and one loopful (1 µL loop) was streaked over the surface of CIN agar (29°C, 24h)
L6	F	Biochemical tests, Bio-/serotyping	PSB (for 3 h) at 25°C. PSB_> 10 µL and 100 µL onto CIN agar. Incubation at 30°C for 24h. PSB is incubated at 4°C. Day 2: from CIN to BS. Day 8: 100 µL PSB to 10 mL MRB incubated at 25°C for 4 days. Day 12: MRB to CIN and day 13 to BS.
L10	F	Biochemical tests	First, streaking of typical colonies (from CIN) on YeCM to differentiate non-pathogenic Ye (BT1A) from pathogenic YE, then biotyping with ISO 10273:2017
L14	F	NA*	NA*
L15	F	NA*	NA*
L1	F + V	Biochemical tests, Maldi-TOF	Direct plating: 1 ml of the sample was streaked onto three plates of agar Yer. These plates were incubated at 30°C for 48 h. Suspected colonies were streaked onto blood agar being incubated at 30°C for 48 h. Enrichment on PSB (peptone, sorbitol and bile salts): 10 ml of the sample were diluted onto 90 ml of PSB and incubated at 25°C during 5 days. After this incubation, 25 µl was streaked onto agar YER being incubated at 30°C for 48 h. Suspected colonies were streaked onto blood agar being incubated at 30°C for 48 h. Enrichment on ITC: 10 ml of the sample diluted on PSB (before being incubated) were diluted onto 90 ml of ITC (1/100 form the original sample) and incubated at 25°C during 48h. After this incubation, 25 µl were streaked onto agar SSDC being incubated at 30°C for 48 h. Suspected colonies were streaked onto blood agar being incubated at 30°C for 48 h.
L9	F + V	NA*	NA*
L5	V	NA*	NA*
L11	V	Maldi-TOF, esculin	
L3	P + F	Biochemical tests, PCR	According to ISO 18867 (Real time PCR for <i>Y. enterocolitica</i> - target ail gene); real time PCR for <i>Y. enterocolitica</i> - <i>ystA</i> and <i>ystB</i> genes
L4	P	Maldi-TOF, Bio-/serotyping	
L7	P	Maldi-TOF, WGS	
L8	P	Maldi-TOF, esculin	
L12	P	Maldi-TOF, esculin, PCR	In-house PCR target ail gene for <i>Y. enterocolitica</i> and <i>Y. pseudotuberculosis</i> .
L13	P	PCR	BD MAX system (extraction and PCR) using enteric bacterial kit and extended enteric bacterial kit

*Analysis not performed